

The next-generation number (NGN) is the fundamental quantity of interest during radiotherapy

L. M. Bilinsky^a

^a*Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship 2.0, Sacramento, CA, 95816, USA*

Abstract

Background: Two long-standing obstacles to accurately modeling solid tumor response to fractionated radiotherapy have been (1) non-uniformity in cellular radiosensitivity, the cells of the tumor interior, including quiescent cells, being less radiosensitive, and (2) the need to accurately model repopulation dynamics. **Methods:** A new model was developed to address these obstacles. It assumes that the effect of a given course of treatment is best described by means of the “next-generation number (NGN)” concept of mathematical biology. **Results:** The model estimates the expected number (X_f) of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells in existence, given a starting number (X_0), following W weeks of treatment using daily fraction size D . By Markov’s Inequality, the tumor control probability (TCP) satisfies $TCP \geq 1 - X_f$, which relation is useful in the $X_f \ll 1$ regime. The model provides a clear-cut criterion by which D could be selected to minimize effects in normal tissues. It also provides insight into which types of tumor are best treated using hypofractionation. Model parameters could be identified from clinical TCP data, as has been done for the linear-quadratic model, or identified from clonogenic assay data. **Conclusions:** Ionizing radiation works, in the mathematical sense, to reduce the number of cancer cells present by modulating the fruitfulness of the process of cellular replication. This process, which usually results in the replacement of one indefinitely clonogenic cancer cell with two at the conclusion of each cell cycle, is rendered less fruitful than normal, so that a cell does not even replace itself, on average, when it attempts to replicate.

1. Introduction

Fractionated radiotherapy, pioneered by Henri Coutard in the 1920s [1], has been a staple of cancer treatment for 100 years. It continues to be an important treatment modality, alongside surgery, chemotherapy, and immunotherapy. In the effort to improve outcomes for fractionated radiotherapy, the development of innovative approaches such as spatial fractionation, the use of ultra-high dose rate, and the use of nanoparticles is of great importance [2]. However, just as important is the development of new mathematical models which better predict how a tumor will respond to a proposed treatment scheme.

In this paper, I argue that, with regard to what is of interest to clinicians, the effect of ionizing radiation upon cancer cells is best understood by means of the “next-generation number” concept of mathematical biology. I use this concept to develop a new equation for predicting the response of a solid tumor to fractionated radiotherapy. The new equation takes into account the fact that cancer cells, located within different regions of the tumor,

have differing radiosensitivities (e.g., quiescent cells of the interior are less radiosensitive than actively replicating cells on the surface). It also circumvents the need to explicitly model repopulation. The equation can be used to determine the daily fraction size and treatment duration that achieves a desired tumor control probability, while maximally sparing normal tissues of concern. My main focus in this paper is the most common fractionation scheme, in which five equal-size fractions are administered per week, 24 hours apart, on Monday through Friday. However, in section 6.4 of the Supplementary Information, I briefly consider ultra-hypofractionation.

2. Methods

All equations were motivated by first principles. Figures were generated using MATLAB R2020b (The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA, 2020).

3. Results

Preliminary remarks

In [3], I developed a new equation to fit clonogenic assay data reporting surviving fraction (SF) versus administered dose (D , typically measured in Grays) of ionizing radiation, for cancer cells exposed *in vitro* to a single dose of ionizing radiation. The new dose-survival equation is a target model, and I argued that, for its purposes, the target is best thought of as the region of the cell membrane which occludes the genome; that is, the region which incoming photons/particles of radiation must pass through, if they are to have a chance at striking the genome and achieving sterilization (i.e., reproductive death of the cancer cell). I assume this going forward, and refer the interested reader to that paper for details.

3.1. Cellular replication as a branching process

During successful cellular replication, one cell (the “parent cell”) becomes two (the “daughter cells”) after a time interval equal to T_D (the “doubling time”). Upon completion of the cell cycle, the parent cell no longer exists as a distinct entity: it has vanished, replaced by daughter cells. This point is obvious, but conceptually crucial to obtaining the results of this paper. Since a cancer cell is indefinitely clonogenic, its successful replication can be defined as its replacement with two indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells.

Consider a cancer cell that is guaranteed to replicate successfully in the absence of treatment. Since it will be replaced with two indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells at the conclusion of its cell cycle, the replication process is deterministic. During exposure to ionizing radiation, this process becomes stochastic (probabilistic), since zero, one, or two indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells may now result. The stochasticity arises from (1) the stochastic nature of radiation emission—the number of particles striking the target varies, even for a given dose, which really just specifies the mean number of particles [3], and (2) variability in how the emitted particles interact with, and impact, the parent cancer cell. See Fig. 1, which depicts cellular replication while “under fire from” ionizing radiation.

Figure 1: **Cancer cell replication during treatment with ionizing radiation is a discrete, stochastic branching process.** In the absence of treatment, each parent cancer cell is replaced with two indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells at the conclusion of the cell cycle. This deterministic process is the “default trajectory”. When ionizing radiation is applied, the number of indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells coming to replace the parent becomes a random variable, in the sense of rolling a die or flipping a coin. In the diagram, the parent cancer cell is in some particular state (quiescent, or else some phase of the cell cycle) when i photons/particles of ionizing radiation strike the target region of its cell membrane. Given this situation, u is the probability of genome damage occurring. When $i = 0$, as in the absence of treatment, $u = 0$ and the default trajectory is taken, with certainty. When $i \neq 0$, we have $u > 0$ and various possibilities arise: the parent cancer cell could be replaced with zero (probability p_0), one (probability p_1), or two (probability p_2) indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells. We have that $p_0 + p_1 + p_2 = 1$. If the parent cancer cell has some ability to repair itself and/or unrepaired damage does not necessarily result in zero indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells, $p_0 < 1$. In this simple figure, indefinitely clonogenic, mutant daughter cells are classed together with ones that are identical to the parent. Each possible outcome in the diagram corresponds to a sequence of directed arrows, and occurs with a probability that is obtained by multiplying together the parameters labeling the arrows. The outcome terminating in a skull-and-crossbones icon is the only one which results in the removal of an indefinitely clonogenic cancer cell from the population. I refer to this outcome as “sterilization” of the parent cancer cell. I formally treat apoptosis, senescence, and metabolic death of the parent cancer cell as special cases of sterilization, their probabilities contributing to p_0 .

3.2. *The next-generation number (NGN) of a cancer cell is the fundamental quantity of interest during radiotherapy*

The number of indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells brought into existence by the one special cell cycle that is directly impacted by ionizing radiation, when a single dose is administered, is thus a stochastic random variable, with sample space $\{0, 1, 2\}$. Its expected value is given by Eq. 4 below, where I reference the parameters in Fig. 1. I shall refer to this quantity as the parent cancer cell’s “next-generation number” (NGN), a concept that is common in mathematical biology.

$$NGN = E[\text{no. indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells}] \quad (1)$$

$$= 0 \cdot up_0 + 1 \cdot up_1 + 2 \cdot up_2 + 2 \cdot (1 - u) \quad (2)$$

$$= 2(1 - up_0) - up_1 \quad (3)$$

$$= 2 SF - up_1 \quad (4)$$

$$\leq 2 SF \quad (5)$$

Eq. 4 corresponds to a single copy of Fig. 1, describing a cancer cell in a particular state (e.g., engaged in some cell cycle task), receiving i strikes to the target region of its cell membrane. We can use Eq. 4 as a basis for constructing a formula for the population-level NGN of an asynchronously replicating set of cancer cells, as a function of D (dose in Grays), by conditioning upon (1) the different cellular states represented within the population and (2) the value of i , which is a Poisson-distributed random variable with mean kD , k being a constant that varies directly with the cross-sectional area of the genome and inversely with the per-photon/per-particle energy of the radiation in use; see [3] for details. However, since standard clonogenic assay data does not distinguish between colonies arising from one, versus two, daughter cells of an irradiated cancer cell, we cannot identify from it $NGN(D)$. Despite this, we still have the useful, population-level analogue to Eq. 5:

$$NGN(D) \leq 2SF(D) \quad (6)$$

where $SF(D)$ is the dose-survival relationship identified from standard clonogenic assay data.

3.2.1. *Population dynamics of a set of plated cancer cells exposed to a single dose of ionizing radiation*

Let us consider the fate of X_0 plated, asynchronously replicating cancer cells, exposed to a single dose D of ionizing radiation (the plating, prior to irradiation, is a setup for the next section). After the conclusion of the one cell cycle during which radiation is actually incident upon the cells, the expected number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells in existence (X_f) will satisfy:

$$X_f = X_0[NGN(D)] \leq X_0[2SF(D)] \quad (7)$$

A dose D is expected to succeed in reducing the number of reproductively viable cancer cells if and only if it causes cells to not even replace themselves, on average, when they attempt to replicate ($NGN(D) < 1$). This requires that D exceed a critical, nonzero threshold value D_C . If $D < D_C$, then the number of cancer cells is actually expected to increase,

underscoring the fact that the pathological replication process triggered by ionizing radiation exists on a continuum with the “normal” replication process occurring in the absence of treatment. We can conservatively estimate D_C as the dose at which $SF = 0.5$.

It is important to realize that, even when $D > D_C$ and $NGN(D) < 1$, some parent cancer cells will still be replaced with either one or two indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells. Some ways that this can occur: (1) the target region of the cell membrane might not be struck by radiation at all, due to the Poisson statistics, (2) any genome damage might be successfully repaired, (3) genome damage might not be repaired, but the damaged cell might evade apoptosis and go on to produce at least one indefinitely clonogenic daughter cell. However, when $NGN(D) < 1$, such scenarios are rare.

3.2.2. Population dynamics of a set of plated cancer cells exposed to fractionated radiation

During fractionated radiotherapy, cancer cells are exposed to radiation repeatedly, in doses termed “fractions.” Typically, radiation is administered every 24 hours, from Monday through Friday, with weekends off. This is sustained for a number of weeks, during which time replication is ongoing. Let us consider how X_0 plated cancer cells would respond to such a regimen; this case serves as a spatially homogeneous preliminary to that of a solid tumor, considered in the next section.

For this situation, in section 6.6 of the Supplementary Information, I argue that the expected number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells in existence (X_f), following W weeks of treatment, would be:

$$X_f = X_0[NGN_W(D)]^W \quad (8)$$

where $NGN_W(D)$ in Eq. 8 is the weekly analogue to the NGN for a single cell cycle, and a single cell. The content of this claim is that $NGN_W(D)$ (by definition, the expected number of indefinitely clonogenic descendants, standing in a cell’s place after one week of treatment) is approximately the same for the different plated cells, despite the fact that they are in different phases. This is shown by establishing that $(SF(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24.7}{T_D}}$ is an upper bound for $NGN_W(D)$, where T_D is the cells’ doubling time, in an argument that does not depend upon the phase a cell was in (different for different cells) when the first fraction was delivered. For simplicity, moving forward, I will identify $NGN_W(D)$ with this upper bound; this is equivalent to providing the following conservative, practical formula for $NGN_W(D)$:

$$NGN_W(D) = (SF(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24.7}{T_D}} \quad (9)$$

Under this definition of $NGN_W(D)$, and aside from the assumption of a linear-quadratic form for $SF(D)$, Eq. 8 is identical with the most commonly used equation to model a tumor’s response to radiotherapy, when “repopulation” is taken into account [4]:

$$X_f = X_0[(SF(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24.7}{T_D}}]^W \quad (10)$$

I emphasize that Eq. 10 is not accurate from fraction to fraction (i.e., from day to day), and its predictions for non-integer values of W should not be taken seriously. This is because cancer cells, which have typical doubling times in the range 17-80 hours [5], can hardly be expected to reattain a state of maximal asynchrony in between fractions that are only 24

hours apart. In section 6.6 of the Supplementary Information, I argue that Eq. 10 is probably reasonably accurate from week to week (i.e., for integer $W \geq 1$).

Eq. 10 should be interpreted as follows: for each of the X_0 indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells initially present, the expected number of its indefinitely clonogenic descendants, standing in its place after W weeks of treatment, is computed by setting $X_0 = 1$ in this equation. On the strength of this, Eq. 10 holds as written, and applies to the entire population of cells.

3.3. Response of a solid tumor to fractionated radiotherapy

Let us now consider the case of a solid tumor. Cancer cells within a solid tumor are not all in the same physical situation: cells nearer the surface are in a less crowded environment, and are better “irrigated” by the blood vasculature. This both puts them in a better position to be able to replicate at all and also, enables them to acquire biomass faster than cancer cells situated deeper within the interior. For a solid tumor, then, we should expect a spectrum of effective (i.e., resource-limited) doubling-time values: cells on the tumor surface should have the shortest doubling time, those a few layers in may have an actual doubling time which is several times larger, while those deep within the interior, if they are even alive, may have effectively stopped replicating. This last class of cells are effectively quiescent (even if not in G_0), and can formally be assigned a doubling time of infinity.

To model the tumor’s response to radiation, we must apply Eq. 8 to each of its layers separately, since the NGN_W may be different for different layers. The question arises of what to write down for the NGN_W of each layer. The results of my previous paper prove useful here. In [3], I proposed that the surviving fraction of a set of asynchronously replicating cells exposed to a single dose of ionizing radiation can be modeled using the following dose-survival equation:

$$SF(D) = p_R SF_R(D) + p_Q SF_Q(D) \quad (11)$$

In this equation, p_R is the proportion of the doubling time a cell spends in the more radiation-sensitive state R (for “replicating,” since rapidly replicating cells typically have p_R larger than slowly replicating cells), while $p_Q = 1 - p_R$ is the proportion it spends in the less radiation-sensitive state Q (for “quiescent,” since quiescent cells have p_Q nearly equal to 1). In [3], I speculate that state R corresponds to times when there is a high demand for ATP hydrolysis within the nucleus, state Q corresponding to all other times. According to this hypothesis, if the doubling time is T_D (in hours), then a cell spends $T_R = p_R T_D$ hours in state R and $T_Q = p_Q T_D$ hours in state Q, per cell cycle.

$SF_R(D)$ and $SF_Q(D)$ are the pure state-R and state-Q dose-survival curves, respectively. For most cell lines, $SF_R(D) = e^{-kD}$ and $SF_Q(D) = e^{-kD} \left(1 + kD + (1 - P_{0Q,2}) \frac{k^2 D^2}{2}\right)$. In these formulas, k is a parameter which depends upon the cross-sectional area of the genome and the per-photon/per-particle energy of the radiation in use. $P_{0Q,2}$ is the probability that a state-Q cell will be sterilized if two photons/particles strike the target region of its cell membrane (the region occluding the genome). Sample fits of Eq. 11 to data sets for various cancer cell lines are shown in Fig. 2, reproduced from [3].

The new dose-survival equation can be exploited to yield a formula for the NGN_W of each layer, as follows. In [3], I argued that T_R is roughly constant across different cell lines, most of the variation in doubling time being due to variation in T_Q , and speculate that state

Figure 2: Sample fits of the new dose-survival equation (Eq. 11) to previously published clonogenic assay data sets. Also shown is the theoretical state-R/state-Q decomposition. Figure reproduced from [3]; see that paper for a detailed explanation. Theoretical state-R dose-survival relationship ($SF_R(D)$) is shown in red and theoretical state-Q dose-survival relationship ($SF_Q(D)$) is shown in blue. The HTB140 cells' data are consistent with more than one fit; see the caption to this figure in [3] for the two possible sets of parameter values.

Q subsumes any time spent by a cell acquiring the necessary biomass for replication. If so, this suggests that T_R is a constant across different tumor layers, while T_Q varies. This implies the following relationship between the actual doubling time of cells within a given tumor layer, $T_{D,act} = T_R + T_{Q,act}$, and $p_{Q,act} = \frac{T_{Q,act}}{T_{D,act}}$, the actual time-proportion of the cell cycle the cells spend in state Q:

$$T_{D,act} = \frac{T_R}{1 - p_{Q,act}} \quad (12)$$

According to this equation, as we descend below the tumor surface and $T_{D,act}$ increases, the dose-survival curve, which is set by the value of $p_{Q,act}$, changes in a predictable way: it shifts away from the red curve and toward the blue curve (see Fig. 2). Substituting $T_{D,act}$ for T_D and $SF_{act}(D) = (1 - p_{Q,act})SF_R(D) + p_{Q,act}SF_Q(D)$ for $SF(D)$ in Eq. 9, we obtain:

$$NGN_W(D, p_{Q,act}) = (SF_{act}(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24 \cdot 7}{T_{D,act}}} \quad (13)$$

$$= ((1 - p_{Q,act})SF_R(D) + p_{Q,act}SF_Q(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24 \cdot 7 \cdot (1 - p_{Q,act})}{T_R}} \quad (14)$$

where in Eq. 14 I have utilized Eq. 12. Eq. 14 gives the weekly next-generation number as a function of daily fraction size D and $p_{Q,act}$, the actual time-proportion of the cell cycle the cells of a given layer spend in state Q. This equation holds for the usual fractionation scheme, in which equal-size fractions are administered Monday through Friday, 24 hours apart, skipping weekends. For remarks on other schemes, see section 6.4 of the Supplementary Information.

To use Eq. 14, we must know T_R for the cancer cells in question. Although roughly constant across different cell types, there might be some variability. In theory, $T_R = p_R T_D$ could be determined for a given type of cancer cell by fitting the new dose-survival equation to its clonogenic assay data, provided the cells' doubling time, during irradiation, was known. However, the error bars are often too large to identify T_R in this way with precision, due to uncertainty in the fitted value of p_R . It is probably more accurate to just set T_R equal to its average value across different cell lines, which I estimated at 18 hours in [3], on the basis of the data sets shown in Fig. 2. Throughout the rest of this paper, I will assume that $T_R = 18$.

Under Eq. 14, each layer of the tumor is associated with a particular value of $p_{Q,act}$, which dictates $NGN_W(D)$ for that layer. Cells on the tumor surface probably have the smallest doubling time realized within the tumor, call it T_D , and thus the smallest value of $p_{Q,act}$. I shall refer to this minimal value of $p_{Q,act}$ as p_Q . As we descend below the tumor surface, both $T_{D,act}$ and $p_{Q,act}$ increase from these minimal values, creating a trade-off in how $NGN_W(D)$ changes: although deeper layers have longer doubling times, reducing the exponent of 2 in Eq. 14, they are more resilient to ionizing radiation, since $SF_{act}(D)$ is shifted more heavily toward the pure state-Q curve.

3.3.1. New model for the response of a solid tumor to fractionated radiotherapy

So long as a set of X_0 cancer cells/their descendants remain within a single tumor layer, as measured from the surface, their population dynamics will be governed by the equation $X_f = X_0 [NGN_W(D, p_{Q,act})]^W$, where $p_{Q,act}$ has some particular value. However, in general, the relative position of a cancer cell and its descendants will change as treatment proceeds

and the tumor shrinks. I propose to get around this problem by viewing all tumor cells as being governed (immediately) by the copy of $X_f = X_0[NGN_W(D, p_{Q,act})]^W$ that governs the layer with the maximal $NGN_W(D, p_{Q,act})$:

$$X_f = X_0[\max(NGN_W)(D)]^W \quad (15)$$

To which tumor layer does $\max(NGN_W)(D)$ belong? Let us inspect Eq. 14. When $D = 0$, the surface layer, as it has the shortest doubling time, corresponding to p_Q . During radiotherapy this situation may change, since state Q is more resilient to low-LET radiation. In section 6.7 of the Supplementary Information, I use calculus to determine $p_{Q,crit}$, the value of $p_{Q,act}$ at which the weekly next-generation number is maximal, for a given value of D . I obtain:

$$p_{Q,crit}(D) = \max \left[p_Q, \frac{5}{c} - \frac{SF_R(D)}{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)} \right] \quad (16)$$

where c is defined as

$$c = \frac{\ln(2) \cdot 24 \cdot 7}{T_R} \approx 6.47 \quad (17)$$

I emphasize that $\max(NGN_W)(D) = NGN_W(D, p_{Q,crit}(D))$ does not correspond to any one particular layer, for all D . Rather, it corresponds to the “winning layer,” for the chosen value of D , wherever it may be located. $\max(NGN_W)(D)$ is useful because it serves as an upper envelope on the various layers’ $NGN_W(D)$ curves, whether or not, for a given value of D , any layer with $p_{Q,act} = p_{Q,crit}(D)$ actually exists. In section 6.7 of the Supplementary Information, I show that, as D increases from zero, $\max(NGN_W)(D)$ continues, for a time, to belong to the surface layer. Eventually, a critical value of D is reached at which the location of the “winning” layer begins to descend inward, so that $p_{Q,crit}(D) > p_Q$. As $D \rightarrow \infty$, $p_{Q,crit}(D) \rightarrow \frac{5}{c} \approx 0.77$. See top panels of Fig. 3 for an illustration of these ideas, for hypothetical tumors comprised of AG6000 ovarian cancer cells (left) and PC3 prostate cancer cells (right), two of the cell lines considered in Fig. 2.

The power of this new approach is as follows. For each of the indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells present when the first fraction is administered, Eq. 15, with $X_0 = 1$, bounds from above the expected number of its indefinitely clonogenic descendants, standing in its place after W weeks of treatment. From this, it follows that Eq. 15, as written, provides an upper bound on the expected number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells in existence after W weeks of treatment. This is illustrated in the middle and bottom panels of Fig. 3, where the black curve represents X_f/X_0 , as computed using Eq. 15, and the colored curves represent X_f/X_0 , computed for various tumor layers.

It is important to note that these results are contingent upon all cells of the tumor being normoxic. In section 6.5 of the Supplementary Information, I discuss strategies for dealing with hypoxic cells, and propose a novel hypothesis for how hyperthermia acts to radiosensitize them.

3.3.2. Implementing the new model

Theoretically, to implement the new model, we must first collect clonogenic assay data for a sample of the tumor’s cells, using the same type of ionizing radiation as will be used

during treatment. Eq. 11 must then be fit to the data and $SF_R(D)$ and $SF_Q(D)$ identified. It is conceivable, but unknown to me at the time of writing, that $SF_Q(D)$ varies slightly with doubling time. This would indicate the existence of different “state-Q microstates,” as discussed in [3]. This does not pose a serious obstacle to the method, as we would just need to define $SF_Q(D)$ as the most radioresistant of the various state-Q curves identified for different confluency (i.e., doubling time) conditions.

We must then estimate T_D , the minimal doubling time attained by any individual cell of the tumor, and use it to compute $p_Q = 1 - \frac{T_R}{T_D}$. $SF_R(D)$, $SF_Q(D)$, and p_Q can then be used to compute the function $p_{Q,crit}(D)$, using Eq. 16. Substituting $p_{Q,crit}(D)$ in for $p_{Q,act}$ in Eq. 14, we obtain $max(NGN_W)(D)$. This implementation, which begins with fitting clonogenic assay data, is intended to clarify the conceptual basis of the new fractionation equation. In practice, $SF_R(D)$ and $SF_Q(D)$ could be identified from clinical tumor control probability data, as is often done for the parameters of the LQ model [6]. I propose a method of doing this in section 6.2 of the Supplementary Information.

3.3.3. Selecting a fraction size, and estimating the tumor control probability

Once we have determined $max(NGN_W)(D)$, we can use Eq. 15 to conservatively estimate X_f after W weeks of treatment. We should aim for X_f to be significantly less than 1. Suppose that we decide $X_f = 0.001$ is good enough. If the original number of cancer cells, X_0 , is one billion, then we must reduce this by 12 decades. The number of weeks’ treatment this requires depends upon D , the daily fraction size. Damage to any normal tissue of interest is minimized if D is selected so that $\frac{NGN_{tiss,W}(D)}{max(NGN_W)(D)}$ is maximal, where $NGN_{tiss,W}(D)$ is the weekly next-generation number of cells of the tissue of interest. For details, and a warning regarding the use of low daily fraction sizes, see section 6.3 of the Supplementary Information.

By Markov’s Inequality, the tumor control probability (TCP) satisfies $TCP \geq 1 - X_f$. This becomes useful when $X_f \ll 1$, as should be the case for any treatment scheme with curative goal. For example, when $X_f = 0.1$, $TCP \geq 0.9$. I note that Markov’s Inequality does not rely upon the probability distribution of the final number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells having any special properties, such as being Poisson.

4. Discussion

The NGN concept provides insight into why some tumors, such as prostate and breast [7], benefit from hypofractionation more than others. A tumor whose $max(NGN_W)(2)$ is relatively large would have to be treated with 2-Gy daily fractions for a very long time before we could be certain of having reduced, by the target number of decades (unless this target is very small), the number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells present. This is the case for the hypothetical prostate tumor, comprised of PC3 cells, considered in Fig. 3. In contrast, the hypothetical ovarian tumor, comprised of AG6000 cells, could be successfully treated using this fraction size, although the treatment duration would be rather long.

5. Conclusions

When a solid tumor is treated with ionizing radiation, we encounter the challenge that, in general, different of its cells will have different doubling times, since their locations determine

Figure 3: **Extension of the NGN_W concept to solid tumors: predicted tumor response to the usual fractionation scheme, in which five identical fractions of size D are administered every 24 hours, Monday-Friday.** I consider hypothetical solid tumors comprised of AG6000 ovarian cancer cells (left panels) or PC3 prostate cancer cells (right panels), two of the cell lines considered in Fig. 2. *Top panels:* $\max(NGN_W)(D)$ (shown in black) serves as an upper envelope on the weekly next-generation numbers of the various tumor layers. It does not correspond to a particular layer, but to the layer possessing the largest $NGN_W(D)$, at a given value of D . When $D = 0$, this is the surface layer (shown in red). As D increases, the surface layer continues to possess the largest $NGN_W(D)$ until D reaches a critical value, at which point the black and red curves diverge. This occurs for both the AG6000 and PC3 tumors, but is not visually obvious for the latter. *Middle and bottom panels:* Ratio of the expected number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells in existence, after W weeks of treatment, to the initial number, for various tumor layers ($X_f/X_0 = [NGN_W(D, p_{Q,act})]^W$). Also plotted (in black) is X_f/X_0 as computed using Eq. 15. Two complications arise when predicting solid tumor response to radiotherapy: (1) Different layers are eliminated at different rates, since they have different $NGN_W(D, p_{Q,act})$ values. (2) The layers in which the current-generation descendants, of a cancer cell originally present, reside changes as treatment proceeds and the tumor shrinks. Eq. 15 addresses both of these issues. *Hypothetical ovarian tumor results:* when using a 2-Gy daily fraction size, treatment must be sustained for 9 weeks to be confident of achieving a 12-decade reduction in cell number (90 Gy total dose). If 3-Gy daily fractions are used instead, only 4 weeks are required for this (60 Gy total dose). *Hypothetical prostate tumor results:* treatment with 2-Gy daily fractions would have to be sustained for an unreasonable length of time to be confident of achieving a 12-decade reduction in cell number. If 3.5-Gy daily fractions are used instead, only 5 weeks are required for this (87.5 Gy total dose). Code available at <https://github.com/lmbilinsky>.

their access to space and nutrients. Indeed, some cells deep within the tumor interior might not be replicating at all. This is problematic because, for a given type of cancer cell, the single-fraction dose-survival relationship, $SF(D)$, changes as the actual (i.e., realized) doubling time, $T_{D,act}$, changes. Direct evidence for this is provided by the trend that is observed when cells are irradiated at different confluencies, a greater confluency producing a curvier dose-survival relationship [8]. This phenomenon, which is more quantitatively significant for large tumors, has been a major obstacle to developing an equation which accurately predicts how a solid tumor will respond to radiotherapy. It may be among the many reasons that treatment failure has been more common for large, versus small, tumors: the equations in common use to plan a course of treatment assume a common $SF(D)$ for all cells, and large tumors deviate more dramatically from this assumption.

The NGN_W approach to modeling a tumor’s response to fractionated radiotherapy overcomes this problem by exploiting the trade-off which exists between radiosensitivity and replication rate: as we descend below the tumor surface and cells become more radioresistant, their replication rate decreases, as described by Eq. 14. For sufficiently large fraction sizes, the two effects nearly cancel, so that NGN_W is approximately the same for all tumor cells. For such D , the cancer cell count declines with time in a simple, exponential way, as if no spatial inhomogeneity were even present.

In conclusion, cellular replication during radiotherapy has traditionally been thought of as “repopulation,” but this term is somewhat misleading. That is because it suggests a separation between the process which acts to reduce the number of cancer cells present, when radiation treatment is in progress, and the process which acts to increase this number, when it is not. In fact, there is only one process, that of cellular replication, and it is ongoing. While a given fractionation schedule is sustained, it modulates this process’s fruitfulness, so that a cancer cell’s weekly next-generation number is much reduced from its no-treatment value; so much so, in fact, that it does not even replace itself, on average, during a treatment week ($NGN_W(D) < 1$). In this way, the process of (attempted) cellular replication, which usually serves to increase the number of cancer cells present, is instead made to reduce it.

6. Supplementary Information

6.1. Remarks regarding the new model of solid tumor response to fractionated radiotherapy

6.1.1. Realism of model assumptions

Three remarks on realism are in order. First, I have spoken of a solid tumor as if it were comprised of well-defined layers, each consisting of cells with a particular doubling time $T_{D,act}$, which increases as we approach the core. This was done for pedagogical reasons but is not essential to the results. Even if cells with different $T_{D,act}$ values (equivalently, $p_{Q,act}$ values) were randomly distributed throughout the tumor, the equations would continue to hold, the “layers,” in this case, really being sets of cells with a common $T_{D,act}$ ($p_{Q,act}$), wherever they may be located. Second, I have spoken of the tumor as if it were a sphere. In fact, the shape of the tumor is not relevant, this simply influencing how the cells are apportioned among the various “layers.” Third, the tumor may or may not actually contain any cells for which $p_{Q,act} = p_{Q,crit}$, for a given D . Regardless, $max(NGN_W)(D)$ serves as a useful upper bound on the weekly next-generation number of all real tumor cells.

6.1.2. Conservative nature of the new model

Underlying Eq. 15 are three assumptions that cause it to be conservative, i.e., to over-estimate X_f/X_0 after W weeks of treatment. First, in writing the expression for the next-generation number of a cancer cell, I have assumed that there is zero probability of it being sterilized in cases where no photons/particles of ionizing radiation strike it or its target; note that this is always possible, at any D , due to the Poisson statistics of particle emission. In reality, some cancer cells will still undergo apoptosis prior to entering their next cell cycle (for reasons not caused by us) or otherwise fail to produce at least one indefinitely clonogenic daughter cell, which outcomes are equivalent to sterilization. Second, when a cell repairs sublethal damage and then re-enters the cell cycle, this adds a bit of time unto its actual doubling time, reducing the power of 2 in Eq. 9. This has been neglected. Third, for each of the original cancer cells present, the actual (i.e., realized) $NGN_W(D)$ values possessed by it/its descendants will change as their positions within the tumor change, through the effect that this has upon $T_{D,act}$. No cell will be such that it, and all of its descendants, possess $max(NGN_W)(D)$ throughout the entire treatment course.

In light of the above considerations, the estimate for X_f/X_0 that Eq. 15 provides is quite conservative. This property is useful, as it compensates for minor deviations from the assumption that cells, while replicating with actual doubling time $T_{D,act}$, have vulnerability to sterilization as described by $SF_{act}(D) = (1 - p_{Q,act})SF_R(D) + p_{Q,act}SF_Q(D)$, where $p_{Q,act} = 1 - \frac{T_R}{T_{D,act}}$. Such deviation constitutes “radiation sampling error.” In section 6.6 I estimate that, for the usual five-day-a-week fractionation scheme, it takes about one week for radiation to accurately sample how cells spend their time, with regard to states Q and R. There are cases where this condition might not be satisfied, for example, that of quiescent cells which only enter the cell cycle in the final week of treatment, not having been sterilized first. The conservative nature of Eq. 15 serves to compensate for those cases in which the bias does not work in our favor (i.e., in which it is toward state Q).

6.2. Identifying model parameters from clinical TCP data

One possible strategy for identifying model parameters (k and the various sterilization probabilities; recall that $p_{Q,act}$ varies throughout the tumor) from clinical outcome data is as follows. First, we must have at our disposal data reporting the TCP which results when a tumor of a given type (i.e., prostate), initially comprised of X_0 indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells, is treated for W weeks with fractionated radiotherapy, using daily fraction size D . Each datum would consist of the triple (X_0, W, D) and the reported value of TCP . Importantly, the photon wavelength/particle energy must be the same for all of these data, since k and the sterilization probabilities vary with it [3]. The sterilization probabilities also vary with the dose rate used; hence, this too must be the same for all data points. These same remarks would apply when attempting to identify the LQ model parameters from clinical TCP data.

Let us assume that we have such a data set. If the tumors which concern us are not comprised of profoundly radioresistant cancer cells (i.e., not like the HTB140 cells of Fig. 2 of the main text, reproduced from [3]), then cells have $SF_R(D) = e^{-kD}$, and it is only the state-Q sterilization probabilities, and k , which must be identified. We would begin the fitting procedure by making an initial guess as to the values of these, just as when fitting Eq. 11 to a clonogenic assay data set. We would also need to estimate T_D , the minimal doubling time (*in vivo*) realized within the tumor, typically by the cells of the surface layer.

Using this information, we would generate the analogue to the figure shown in either of the top panels of Fig. 3 (main text).

Referencing this figure, for each of the (X_0, W, D) triples, we would predict a range of values within which X_f , the expected number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells at the conclusion of treatment, should have fallen. We would do this by computing $X_f = X_0[NGN_W(D, p_{Q,act})]^W$ for each allowable value of $p_{Q,act}$ (i.e., for each tumor layer), the set of resulting X_f forming our predicted range. Depending upon the initial tumor size and geometry, the actual X_f should have fallen somewhere within this range. For example, a very small tumor might have had X_f approximately equal to $X_f = X_0[NGN_W(D, p_Q)]^W$, the value as computed using the surface layer's $NGN_W(D)$, for which $p_{Q,act} = p_Q = 1 - \frac{T_R}{T_D}$. A larger tumor might have had X_f lying closer to the value as computed using the quiescent layer's $NGN_W(D)$.

This being done, we would then plot, for each triple, the predicted X_f range on the x-axis, using horizontal error bars, and the associated, reported TCP value on the y-axis. Model parameters (k , $P_{0Q,2}$, $P_{0Q,3}$, etc.) would then be varied until this plot looks “maximally reasonable,” meaning that a clear trend is discernible, despite significant scatter, wherein TCP decreases monotonically with X_f . We also have the constraint imposed by Markov’s Inequality ($TCP \geq 1 - X_f$), which the plotted data must satisfy. Triples obtained using distinct daily fraction sizes are necessary to identify model parameters.

Regarding scatter, it is unsurprising if, for a common predicted value of X_f , there is a significant spread in the reported TCP values, or vice versa. This would just indicate that the number of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells at the conclusion of treatment has a probability distribution which can vary significantly for different individual tumors and instances of treatment. It is often assumed that this distribution is Poisson, so that one can identify model parameters by means of the relationship $TCP = e^{-X_f}$. However, this is not really justified, and is unnecessary. The choice of model parameter values that “maximizes the signal to noise ratio,” as judged qualitatively, when the reported TCP and the predicted X_f range are plotted against one another will be closer to the true values than the ones which result when the relationship between X_f and TCP is constrained to be of any particular form.

Once identified, it is important to remember that these parameter values are only good for a particular type of radiation (photon wavelength, etc.) and dose rate. However, k , once identified for a particular type of low-LET radiation, can probably be scaled in a straightforward way to obtain its value for a different type of radiation (whose per-photon/per-particle energy is different; see [3], where I provide the formula for k). This might do much to aid in identifiability of the remaining parameter values (i.e., the sterilization probabilities for different numbers of strikes).

6.3. Selecting a fraction size which minimizes damage to normal tissues of interest

Eq. 15 tells us the number of weeks of treatment required for us to be reasonably certain of reducing X_f/X_0 by a target number of decades, when using daily fraction size D . By this time, those tumor layers whose $NGN_W(D)$ is significantly smaller than $\max(NGN_W)(D)$ will have been dramatically depopulated. The middle panels of Fig. 3 (main text) illustrate this phenomenon. For the hypothetical ovarian tumor, the significant spread which exists at $D = 2$ in the value of NGN_W for different tumor layers results in a situation where, by the

time we can be certain of having reduced X_f/X_0 by 12 decades, some layers will have had their cell count reduced by 14 decades or more. When using a daily fraction size of 3 Gy, this effect is only minor. The effect is also seen for the hypothetical prostate tumor, being extreme when $D = 2$ and relatively minor when $D = 3.5$.

This phenomenon suggests a criterion by which D can be selected to minimize damage to normal tissues. First, let us consider slowly-responding tissues. Tissues with a low rate of cellular turnover can be viewed as quiescent on the time scale of treatment, and assigned a $NGN_{tiss,W}(D)$ accordingly: $NGN_{tiss,W}(D) = [SF_{tiss,Q}(D)]^5$, where $SF_{tiss,Q}(D)$ is the pure state-Q dose-survival relationship for the normal tissue cells. If D is chosen so that $\frac{NGN_{tiss,W}(D)}{\max(NGN_W)(D)}$ is maximal, then normal tissue cells will have the greatest possible advantage (or least possible disadvantage) over the tumor cells. This choice of D maximizes $X_{tiss,f}/X_{tiss,0} = [NGN_{tiss,W}(D)]^W$, which serves as a measure of healthy tissue preservation at the conclusion of treatment. In this equation, W is whatever number weeks' treatment is necessary to reduce, by the target number of decades, the number of tumor cells, when using daily fraction size D . In employing this criterion, it is not necessary to know $X_{tiss,0}$, the number of healthy tissue cells normally present.

Let us consider an example. Suppose that normal prostate cells had the same $SF_Q(D)$ as PC3 prostate cancer cells. Then, their $NGN_{tiss,W}(D)$ would be identical to the $NGN_W(D)$ for quiescent PC3 cells (navy blue curve appearing in the top right panel of Fig. 3 of the main text). If our goal were to maximally preserve normal prostate cells, then $D = 3.5$ (bottom right panel) would be a much better choice than $D = 2$ (middle right panel).

In general, for any particular type of late-responding tissue, if our goal were to maximally preserve it during treatment, we would achieve this by (1) carrying out a cell survival assay for the normal tissue cells and identifying their $SF_Q(D)$, (2) plotting $NGN_{tiss,W}(D) = [SF_Q(D)]^5$ alongside $\max(NGN_W)(D)$ for the tumor cells, and (3) selecting D to maximize $\frac{NGN_{tiss,W}(D)}{\max(NGN_W)(D)}$. Although, for a given total dose D_{total} , smaller fractions are, in general, more sparing of slowly-responding tissues, our goal is not to administer some fixed total dose D_{total} , but rather, to reduce the number of cancer cells present by a target number of decades. If a value of D is selected that is smaller than the optimal value as identified above, the increase in W this necessitates outweighs the benefit apparent in the single-fraction dose-survival relationship.

The tissue-preservation criterion can also be employed for early-responding tissues, where stem cell preservation is the typical concern. In computing $NGN_{stem,W}(D)$, stem cells should be treated as quiescent as regards doubling time, since when they replicate, they only replace themselves. However, $SF_Q(D)$ should not be used for them, since they are in fact replicating, and using it would overestimate their resilience. Stem cells should be assigned $NGN_{stem,W}(D) = [SF(D)]^5$, where $SF(D)$ is their single-fraction dose-survival relationship, identified under culture conditions for which they have their *in vivo* doubling time (equivalently, replication rate). According to the tissue-preservation criterion, the stem cell population is maximally preserved when D is selected so that $\frac{NGN_{stem,W}(D)}{\max(NGN_W)(D)}$ is maximal.

6.3.1. $NGN_W(D) > 1$ breeds mutants

Regardless of which fraction size D we select, it must not be such that some cells within the tumor have $NGN_W(D) > 1$. This is primarily a concern for tumors comprised of cells

which are relatively radioresistant and which have short doubling time in some layers (typically, the surface); at small fraction sizes, the surface cells would have $NGN_W(D) > 1$. Cells with $NGN_W(D) > 1$ actually increase in number during radiation therapy, just more slowly than in the absence of treatment, and can be expected to rapidly accumulate mutations as they do. This is because, when ionizing radiation strikes a cancer cell, it is a kind of experiment. The desired outcome of this experiment is sterilization, but another possible outcome is the production of at least one mutated, indefinitely clonogenic daughter cell. When $NGN_W(D) < 1$, the number of “experiments” we must perform, in administering each fraction, at least decreases with time (i.e., the number of viable cancer cells is decreasing), so that we might avoid creating a viable mutant before all cells are sterilized. When $NGN_W(D) > 1$, it is virtually guaranteed that a viable mutant will eventually be produced.

This state of affairs might not be caught by imaging, since the tumor would still be observed to shrink, if most cells had $NGN_W(D) < 1$. However, it would eventually reach a size that the treatment regimen would be unable to reduce further. Its cell count, in this final state, would represent a dynamic equilibrium (the surface cells more than replacing themselves, the interior cells having $NGN_W(D) < 1$) whose genetic composition could change with each fraction. To avoid this scenario, we must not overestimate T_D , the shortest doubling time realized within the tumor; recall that this sets the value of p_Q , the lower bound on $p_{Q,crit}$. T_{POT} cannot be substituted for T_D , since it represents the average, rather than minimal, doubling time of cells of the growth fraction. $max(NGN_W)(D)$ should probably be computed under the assumption that T_D is the cells’ *in vitro* doubling time during exponential growth. At larger daily fraction sizes, there is much less spread in the $NGN_W(D)$ values for the different tumor layers, as shown in Fig. 3 (main text), and this assumption does not cause a tremendous overestimation of $max(NGN_W)(D)$.

6.4. Ultra-hypofractionation

Strongly hypofractionated treatment schemes use fewer than the usual five fractions per week. If $n \neq 5$ fractions are used, then the analogues to Eq. 14 and Eq. 16 are obtained by replacing the 5 in these equations with n . However, for these formulas to be valid, radiation must “sample” cellular state (Q or R) in a way that accurately reflects how cells spend their time during the week, given their actual doubling time $T_{D,act}$ (i.e., approximately $p_{Q,act} = 1 - \frac{T_R}{T_{D,act}}$ of the fractions must catch the cells in state Q). This requires that radiation be administered at roughly regularly spaced intervals throughout the week, and with sufficient frequency. I am skeptical that this condition can be satisfied when fewer than five fractions are administered per week.

For sparsely-fractionated treatment schemes, I suggest that $SF_Q(D)$, the pure state-Q dose-survival relationship, be used to model the effect of each fraction. Since each cell of the tumor is in either state Q or state R when a given fraction is administered, $SF_Q(D)$ serves as an upper bound on the whole-tumor surviving fraction. When taking this approach, we must explicitly model the ongoing process of cellular replication (“repopulation”) using, for example, the logistic or Gompertz models, or the exponential model with T_{POT} .

6.5. Strategies for dealing with hypoxic cells

6.5.1. Shell approach

In the “shell approach,” we would begin by estimating the number of normoxic cancer cells of a tumor, $X_{norm,0}$, from imaging data or geometric considerations. This subpopulation of tumor cells can, for illustrative purposes, be thought of as occupying an outer shell. Radiotherapy must be sustained until these cells have been both sterilized, and physically removed from the tumor, via apoptosis or mitotic catastrophe; recall that the latter might not occur until four or five doubling times have elapsed, after the point of sterilization. Once the first normoxic shell is no longer physically present, we would re-image the tumor to determine the new $X_{norm,0}$, repeating this process until $X_f \ll 1$.

A variant of this approach is to pause treatment once the normoxic shell has been sterilized, only resuming radiotherapy once its layers have “peeled off.” The rest of the tumor, comprised of initially hypoxic cells, might grow somewhat during this pause, but it is likely that the total number of fractions needed to achieve a given $X_f \ll 1$, under this approach, is still smaller than when radiation is applied continually.

I emphasize that a formal treatment of the hypoxic status is necessary, if we are to be confident of eliminating all cancer cells. To see why, consider a particular cancer cell, hypoxic when treatment begins. This cell, if not sterilized first, will eventually encounter a fraction that finds it in the oxygenated state. However, by the time that this occurs, the true resilience of this cell, against all of the preceding fractions, will have been vastly underestimated by any model that assumes a normoxic radiation response (e.g., Eq. 15, with $SF_R(D)$ and $SF_Q(D)$ as identified for normoxic cells, or the LQ model, with α and β as identified for normoxic cells) throughout. With the shell approach, we do not rely upon radiation being at all effective against a given cancer cell until it is normoxic. That said, the need to exclude hypoxic cells from the modeled effects of radiotherapy is inconvenient. Hyperthermia, discussed next, might dispense with the need for this.

6.5.2. Hyperthermia

It is well known that hyperthermia is highly effective at sensitizing hypoxic cells to ionizing radiation [9]. Here, I propose a novel hypothesis for this phenomenon. In [3], I argued that the mechanical resilience of the nuclear envelope is a major determinant of cellular sensitivity to ionizing radiation. I also speculated that water cluster size, of the water within the perinuclear space, influences this resilience, with larger water clusters serving to stabilize the nuclear envelope in an effect that is mediated by hydrogen bonding.

Yuan et al. [10] showed that, as the concentration of oxygen dissolved in water decreases, average water cluster size increases. In light of this, an increased water cluster size in the perinuclear space during hypoxia may be a major mechanism by which hypoxia increases radioresistivity. The royal road to reducing water cluster size is of course hyperthermia, and its use would enforce a normoxic water cluster size in the perinuclear space of hypoxic cells. If hyperthermia transforms the ultra-resistant hypoxic dose-survival relationship into one which is largely identical with the normoxic $SF_Q(D)$, pre-treatment of a large tumor’s core with hyperthermia, prior to every fraction, might entirely overcome the unique challenge posed by hypoxic cells, and enable us to accurately model the entire tumor with Eq. 15.

6.6. Argument for the validity of Eq. 10

In [3], I introduced a new dose-survival equation to fit clonogenic assay data collected for irradiated cells. I showed that the linear-quadratic (LQ) model is an approximation to this new equation that can be obtained by taking a Taylor expansion. The new equation, of form $SF(D) = p_R SF_R(D) + p_Q SF_Q(D)$, is motivated by the hypothesis that all cellular activities can be partitioned into two states, which I call “state R” and “state Q.” These differ in their sensitivity to low-LET radiation, state R being the more radiosensitive of the two states. In the equation, $SF_R(D)$ ($SF_Q(D)$) is the dose-survival relationship for cells in state R (state Q), and p_R (p_Q) is the time-proportion of the cell cycle the cells spend in state R (state Q). Although not strictly necessary to the argument for Eq. 10, the argument is made clearer if we accept the new dose-survival equation and the state-Q/state-R hypothesis which motivates it. I will do so in what follows.

Suppose that we plate X_0 cancer cells and irradiate them every 24 hours, from Monday through Friday, skipping weekends, sustaining this regimen for several weeks. At the moment the first fraction is administered, cellular replication can be expected to be maximally asynchronous. Hence, we can expect p_Q of the cancer cells to be in state Q, and p_R to be in state R. This enables us to use the new dose-survival equation to compute $SF_1(D)$, the surviving fraction following the first fraction of radiation: it is just $SF(D) = p_R SF_R(D) + p_Q SF_Q(D)$. The problem is how to describe the effects of fractions beyond the first. Let us define $SF_2(D)$ as the fraction of indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells, in existence at the time of the second fraction, which reproductively survive it.

We have that $SF_2(D) = p_{2Q} SF_Q(D) + (1 - p_{2Q}) SF_R(D)$, where p_{2Q} is the fraction of indefinitely clonogenic cells, in existence at the time of the second fraction, in state Q at this time. We cannot assume that $p_{2Q} = p_Q$, since the first fraction of low-LET radiation breaks the property of asynchrony, being, as it is, more effective against cells in state R than state Q. Of course, the state of maximal asynchrony will eventually be reattained, due to random fluctuations in the time it takes to complete various cellular tasks. However, 24 hours is not sufficient for this, given that typical *in vitro* doubling times are in the range of 17-80 hours [5]. We can therefore expect p_{2Q} to be different from p_Q . The same problem occurs for the third fraction and, indeed, all fractions beyond the first.

We can visualize this situation as follows; for this discussion, please refer to either of the cancer wheels appearing in Fig. 4. Imagine that the cancer wheel is the face of a clock and that this clock has one hand (not shown), which moves clockwise, completing a revolution every T_D hours, where T_D is the doubling time of the plated cancer cells. Situated along the length of the hand are the cells, all in different phases of their cell cycles, with each phase corresponding to one particular track of the cancer wheel. As the hand on the cancer wheel moves clockwise, the cells move with it. Each cell, upon exiting the mitotic region of its track (not shown), is replaced with at most two indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells. Thus, new cells are added to the population at all times, and the total number of cells doubles, at most, with each revolution. This is how things proceed in the absence of treatment.

Now, let us consider the effect of fractionated radiation upon the cells. We can do this by means of the following analogy. Imagine that the clockhand is electrified. Usually, the current through it is turned off, but when a fraction of radiation is administered, it turns on, exposing the cells lying along its length to a risk of sterilization, which we can think of as disappearance from the clockhand. For each cell, the probability that it will be sterilized

by a particular “zap” depends upon whether it is in state Q (white region of track) or state R (blue region) when radiation strikes.

We shall consider the reproductive fate of some particular cancer cell, present at the time the first fraction of radiation is administered. Let us administer the first fraction at noon on Monday, assigning this point in time to the “twelve o’clock” position on the clockface. The cancer cell in question occupies some particular track of the cancer wheel, determined by its cell cycle phase. The first “zap,” delivered when the hand is at “twelve o’clock,” sterilizes the cell with probability $1 - SF_Q(D)$ if it is on a white region of track at this time, and probability $1 - SF_R(D)$ if it is on a blue region. Whether the region is blue or white is not a matter of probability, since we have picked out a *particular* track of the cancer wheel.

If our cancer cell escapes sterilization, it will continue to move with the clockhand. Suppose that the doubling time of the cells in question is $T_D = 36$ hours. Then at noon on Tuesday, 24 hours later, the clockhand will have advanced by two-thirds of a revolution, so that it reads “eight o’clock” when the next fraction is administered. The cell’s probability of surviving this second zap, in the reproductive sense, depends upon whether “eight o’clock” corresponds to a blue or white region of its track. The process then continues. Radiation is typically not administered over the weekend, which fact can be accommodated by viewing Saturday and Sunday as “sham” days, on which the scheduled zap is skipped. *If* the cancer cell completes mitosis (not shown, but could be thought of as a “finish line” drawn on the track) without being sterilized first, it will be replaced with either one or two indefinitely clonogenic daughter cells. This constitutes the first generation of the original, now-vanished, cancer cell’s descendants.

The process then continues, with second-, third-, and higher-generation descendants possibly being brought into existence. Let us refer to the sequence $O \rightarrow D_1 \rightarrow D_2 \rightarrow \dots$ as a “line of descent” of the original cell, where O is the original parent cancer cell, D_1 is one of its indefinitely clonogenic daughters, D_2 is one of the indefinitely clonogenic daughters of the cell labeled D_1 , etc. After g (for “generation”) doubling times have elapsed, there are 2^g possible lines of descent. For any one of them, the question arises: “what is the probability that it is extant?” where “extant” means that the g ’th-generation member exists and is indefinitely clonogenic.

To compute this, we would need to know the sequence of states the line of descent occupied (e.g., “white, blue, blue, white,...”) at the times radiation was administered. If cellular replication proceeded “like clockwork,” this would not, in general, be representative of how the cells spend their time overall (p_Q of it on the white regions of the cancer wheel, $p_R = 1 - p_Q$ of it on the blue regions). Luckily, cellular replication does not proceed like clockwork: there are fluctuations in the time required for different cell-cycle tasks and checkpoints, and in the time required to repair sublethal damage, when it occurs.

Mathematically, we can think of this situation as one in which the doubling time is equal to T_D , but where, overlaid unto this deterministic process, is random phase drift, which serves to advance or retard, relative to where it “should” be at the time a given fraction is administered, a line of descent’s (i.e., its current-generation member’s) position within its track. This random element has the effect of causing the sampling of cell cycle phases by radiation to be more representative of the cell cycle as a whole, provided the sampling roughly covers the entire track.

By when can we expect the sampling to become representative, for the usual fractionation

Figure 4: **“State Q versus state R” hypothesis. Figure and caption reproduced from [3].** A cancer cell’s progression through the cell cycle can be depicted using a “cancer wheel” diagram. Imagine the cancer wheel as a clock-face with a hand (not shown) which moves clockwise, completing one revolution every T_D hours (the doubling time). Each cancer cell, or set of synchronized cells, occupies one track of the cancer wheel. As the hand moves, cells move with it, progressing through the cell cycle. The dose-survival relationship that has been observed for low-LET radiation can be explained by the hypothesis that the cell cycle can be partitioned into two states, which differ in their sensitivity to low-LET radiation. I call these state R and state Q. When a cell is in state R (blue part of track), it will be sterilized if the target region of the cell membrane receives even one strike of low-LET radiation. When a cell is in state Q (white part of track), more than one strike is needed for this. If a population of cancer cells features maximally asynchronous replication, then all tracks will be equally occupied at the time of irradiation. Hence, $p_Q = \frac{T_Q}{T_Q + T_R}$ of the cells will be on a white region of track and $p_R = 1 - p_Q$ of the cells will be on a blue region, where T_R is the time-duration of state R, T_Q is the time-duration of state Q, and $T_D = T_Q + T_R$. If T_R is more highly conserved than T_Q across different cell lines, a trend will be observed wherein p_Q is larger for cells with longer doubling times (more slowly replicating cells), causing them to have a curvier dose-survival relationship. *Left panel:* A hypothetical cancer cell line with doubling time 54 hours. 18 of these are spent in state R and 36 are spent in state Q. Hence, $p_R = 1/3$ and $p_Q = 2/3$. *Right panel:* A hypothetical cancer cell line with doubling time 180 hours; this is an extreme example, intended to illustrate the concept. The duration of state R is still 18 hours but the duration of state Q is now 162 hours. Hence, $p_R = 0.1$ and $p_Q = 0.9$. In this diagram, each cancer wheel track is partitioned into a single white region and a single blue region. This was done for simplicity. The true pattern is more fragmented, since each phase of the cell cycle is comprised of blue and white regions.

scheme, in which one fraction is administered Monday through Friday, every 24 hours? If the state-Q/state-R pattern were as depicted in Fig. 4, I would say after about two weeks, for cells with a doubling time in the typical *in vitro* range of 17-80 hours [5], or cells with $T_{D,act} \approx$ one week, as might be found within the interior. I arrive at this estimate by considering, for such doubling times, the angle on a cancer wheel that is swept out by the “clockhand” over the 24-hour interval between successive fractions, overlaying atop this angle a typical phase drift (which could either advance or retard the phase), and determining how many such “cuts” of the clockhand, upon the “cancer wheel pie,” are needed for them to be roughly evenly spaced and span 360 degrees. In addition to being evenly spaced, the sampling should not be too coarse, as compared with the magnitude of the phase drift. Two weeks, corresponding to ten fractions (“cuts” in the analogy), is probably sufficient.

Assuming that the sampling is representative, then after n fractions have been administered, the probability of a given line of descent being extant satisfies:

$$P_{extant} \leq [SF_Q(D)]^{p_Q n} \cdot [SF_R(D)]^{p_R n} = [(SF_Q(D))^{p_Q} \cdot (SF_R(D))^{p_R}]^n \quad (18)$$

where the inequality stems from the fact that SF represents the probability of a union of events (i.e., that the irradiated, current-generation member of the given line of descent will, upon exiting mitosis, be replaced with indefinitely clonogenic daughter cell “A” and/or indefinitely clonogenic daughter cell “B”), only one of which (e.g., creation of daughter cell “A”) continues the particular line of descent we are considering. $(SF_Q(D))^{p_Q} \cdot (SF_R(D))^{p_R}$ is actually the *geometric mean* of the set of n experienced survival probabilities, p_Q of which are $SF_Q(D)$ and p_R of which are $SF_R(D)$. More familiar is the arithmetic mean, here equal to $p_Q SF_Q(D) + p_R SF_R(D)$. It is a mathematical fact that the arithmetic mean of a set of numbers is greater than or equal to the geometric mean; hence, the following inequality is justified:

$$P_{extant} \leq [p_Q SF_Q(D) + p_R SF_R(D)]^n \quad (19)$$

Suppose that radiotherapy has been ongoing for W weeks. We can formulate an expression for X_f , the expected number of indefinitely clonogenic descendants of the original parent cancer cell, now standing in its place, as follows. During the W weeks of treatment, $n = 5W$ fractions were administered. Cellular replication was ongoing, and $g = \frac{24 \cdot 7W}{T_D}$ doubling times elapsed, on average, giving rise to 2^g possible extant lines of descent. Each of the 2^g possible current-generation descendants of our original cancer cell is associated with a Bernoulli random variable. This equals 1 if the descendant exists (probability P_{extant}) and 0 otherwise, and thus has expected value P_{extant} . X_f is the expected value of the sum of these Bernoulli indicator variables. By the linearity of expected value, we have:

$$X_f = P_{extant} \cdot 2^g \quad (20)$$

$$\leq (p_Q SF_Q(D) + p_R SF_R(D))^{5W} \cdot 2^{\frac{24 \cdot 7W}{T_D}} = \left[(SF(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24 \cdot 7}{T_D}} \right]^W \quad (21)$$

where $SF(D)$ is the single-fraction dose-survival relationship. The state-Q/state-R theory of my previous paper was not essential to deriving Eq. 21, but made the exposition of this section clearer.

Earlier in this section, I speculated that two weeks of treatment, corresponding to ten fractions, is probably necessary for radiation to sample cell cycle phase in a manner that is representative of the cell cycle as a whole. This would suggest that Eq. 21 is only reliable over two-week stretches (i.e., at $W = 2$, $W = 4$, etc.). In fact, the situation is probably much better than this. Strictly speaking, for Eq. 21 to be reliable, radiation need only sample cellular state in a way that representative with regard to state Q and state R, not cell cycle phase *per se*, and the true state-Q/state-R pattern is probably much more fragmented than shown in Fig. 4: in [3], I speculate that state-R activities are ones for which there is a high demand for ATP hydrolysis within the nucleus. If so, then state-R activities (blue regions) should be sprinkled throughout all phases of the cell cycle. Fragmentation of the blue/white pattern would serve to reduce the error that results when radiation only samples, with sufficient fineness, a portion of a given cancer wheel track that subtends significantly less than the full 360 degrees.

In light of this, the accuracy of Eq. 21 can probably be relied upon from week to week (i.e., for integer values of W , where $W \geq 1$). Effectively, this assumes that a one-week treatment stretch is long enough for the effect of cell cycle phase, on radiation response, to “average out,” so that different cancer cells, in different phases at the time of the first fraction (and thenceforth), have approximately the same X_f after one week. Thus, we can meaningfully speak of a (same) weekly next-generation number ($NGN_W(D)$) for the cells, and assert that $X_f = [NGN_W(D)]^W$ for each of them, Eq. 21 serving as an upper bound on this.

Now that we have established Eq. 21 for a single cancer cell, it follows, from the linearity of expected value, that if X_0 indefinitely clonogenic cancer cells are originally present, then after W weeks of treatment the expected final number (X_f) obeys:

$$X_f \leq X_0 \left[(SF(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24.7}{T_D}} \right]^W \quad (22)$$

In Eq. 10 of the main text, I write this as an equality, with the understanding that the true $NGN_W(D)$ has been replaced with (i.e., defined as, for practical purposes) its upper bound, $(SF(D))^5 \cdot 2^{\frac{24.7}{T_D}}$.

6.7. Determination of $p_{Q,crit}$

Consider the usual fractionation scheme, in which equal-size fractions of ionizing radiation are administered Monday-Friday, 24 hours apart, for W weeks. By Eq. 14, each cell of the tumor has a NGN_W which depends upon the daily fraction size D and the actual (i.e., realized) time-proportion of the cell cycle that the cell spends in state Q ($p_{Q,act}$). For illustrative purposes, we can think of the tumor as being like an onion, comprised of various layers, each of which contains cells with a common value of $p_{Q,act}$. $p_{Q,act}$ is generally smallest for the cells of the surface layer; let us call this smallest value p_Q . As we descend toward deeper layers, $p_{Q,act}$ increases, attaining the value of 1 for tumors large enough to contain quiescent cells. Let us treat D as a constant in Eq. 14, and take the derivative with respect to $p_{Q,act}$. We obtain:

$$NGN'_W = 5SF^4(D)(SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)) \cdot 2^{\frac{(1-p_{Q,act}) \cdot 24 \cdot 7}{T_R}} + SF^5(D) \cdot 2^{\frac{(1-p_{Q,act}) \cdot 24 \cdot 7}{T_R}} \cdot \left(\frac{-\ln(2) \cdot 24 \cdot 7}{T_R} \right) \quad (23)$$

$$= \frac{5}{SF(D)}(SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D))NGN_W - \left(\frac{\ln(2) \cdot 24 \cdot 7}{T_R} \right) NGN_W \quad (24)$$

$$= NGN_W \left(5 \frac{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)}{SF(D)} - c \right) \quad (25)$$

$$= NGN_W \left(5 \frac{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)}{(1-p_{Q,act})SF_R(D) + p_{Q,act}SF_Q(D)} - c \right) \quad (26)$$

$$= NGN_W \left(5 \frac{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)}{SF_R(D) + p_{Q,act}(SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D))} - c \right) \quad (27)$$

where $c = \frac{\ln(2) \cdot 24 \cdot 7}{T_R} \approx 6.47$, assuming $T_R = 18$. NGN'_W vanishes when $p_{Q,act} = p_{Q,critcand}$ (for “critical value candidate”), given below.

$$p_{Q,critcand}(D) = \frac{5}{c} - \frac{SF_R(D)}{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)} \quad (28)$$

Inspection of Eq. 27 indicates that, for $p_{Q,act} < p_{Q,critcand}(D)$, $NGN'_W > 0$, while for $p_{Q,act} > p_{Q,critcand}(D)$, $NGN'_W < 0$. Hence, NGN_W is maximal at $p_{Q,critcand}(D)$. It is possible for $p_{Q,critcand}(D)$ to be less than any allowable value of $p_{Q,act}$. For example, it could be negative, or just less than p_Q , the value associated with the surface cells. Taking this constraint into account, the value of $p_{Q,act}$ at which NGN_W is maximal is:

$$p_{Q,crit}(D) = \max \left[p_Q, \frac{5}{c} - \frac{SF_R(D)}{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)} \right] \quad (29)$$

The typical behavior of $p_{Q,crit}$, as a function of D , is as follows. When $D = 0$, $p_{Q,crit} = p_Q$, and NGN_W is largest for the surface cells (which have the smallest actual doubling time, T_D , related to p_Q via $T_D = \frac{T_R}{1-p_Q}$); NGN_W decreases monotonically as we penetrate the tumor. As D increases, $p_{Q,crit}$ eventually moves into the range corresponding to interior layers, reflecting the fact that state Q is more resilient to ionizing radiation than state R. As D approaches infinity, $\frac{SF_R(D)}{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)} \rightarrow 0$, so that $p_{Q,crit}$ approaches $\frac{5}{c} \approx 0.77$. This is illustrated in Fig. 5 for the hypothetical solid tumors considered in Fig. 3 of the main text. Incidentally, this analysis indicates that, for the usual five-day-per-week fractionation scheme, the layer with the largest NGN_W is always some replicating layer, rather than the quiescent layer. Note that, if a tumor is slow-growing enough that $p_Q \geq \frac{5}{c} \approx 0.77$, then the surface layer will always possess the largest NGN_W , no matter how large D becomes.

References

- [1] N. Ghaderi, J. Jung, S. C. Brüningk, A. Subramanian, L. Nassour, and J. Peacock. A century of fractionated radiotherapy: How mathematical oncology can break the rules. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23: article no.1316, 2022.
- [2] H. Ghaznavi, M. Rezaee, F. Reynoso, and A. Darafsheh. Emerging strategies in radiation therapy: promises and challenges of spatial fractionation, ultra-high dose rates, and nanoparticles. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 58(41), 2025.

Figure 5: $p_{Q,crit}(D) = \max \left[p_Q, \frac{5}{c} - \frac{SF_R(D)}{SF_Q(D) - SF_R(D)} \right]$ as a function of daily fraction size D for the hypothetical solid tumors considered in Fig. 3 of the main text. *Top*: For the hypothetical ovarian tumor, the location of the layer possessing the largest weekly next-generation number descends below the tumor surface, where $p_Q = 0.25$, when the daily fraction size reaches 1.894 Gy. *Bottom*: For the hypothetical prostate tumor, $p_Q = 0.5$, and the surface layer possesses the largest weekly next-generation number until the fraction size reaches 2.84 Gy. For both hypothetical tumors, as the daily fraction size increases, $\max(NGN_W)$ belongs to deeper and deeper layers, asymptotically approaching a depth for which $p_{Q,act} \approx 0.77$ (this assumes that $T_R = 18$ hours, so that $c \approx 6.47$). The rate of approach, as D increases, is different for the two cell lines because of differences in their $SF_R(D)$ and $SF_Q(D)$ functions (shown in Fig. 2 of the main text).

- [3] L. M. Bilinsky. A simple new alternative to the linear-quadratic model (and where the LQ model comes from). *Biomath*, 14: article no. 2507035, 2025.
- [4] J. F. Fowler. The linear-quadratic formula and progress in fractionated radiotherapy. *Br. J. Radiol.*, 62:679–694, 1989.
- [5] National Cancer Institute. Doubling time of the NCI set of 60 cancerous cell lines (online), 2024.
- [6] C. M. van Leeuwen, A. L. Oei, J. Crezee, A. Bel, N. A. P. Franken, L. J. A. Stalpers, and H. P. Kok. The alfa and beta of tumours: a review of parameters of the linear-quadratic model, derived from clinical radiotherapy studies. *Radiat Oncol*, 13: article no. 96, 2018.
- [7] D. H. Brand, A. M. Kirby, J. R. Yarnold, and N. Somaiah. How low can you go? The radiobiology of hypofractionation. *Clinical Oncology*, 34:280–287, 2022.
- [8] N. A. P. Franken, S. Hovingh, H. Rodermond, L. Stalpers, G. W. Barendsen, and J. Crezee. Radiosensitization with chemotherapeutic agents and hyperthermia: effects on linear-quadratic parameters of radiation cell survival curves. *Journal of Cancer Science and Therapy*, S5:002, 2011.
- [9] P. B. Elming, B. S. Sorensen, A. L. Oei, N. A. P. Franken, J. Crezee, J. Overgaard, and M. R. Horsman. Hyperthermia: The optimal treatment to overcome radiation resistant hypoxia. *Cancers*, 11(1), 2019.
- [10] H. Yuan, Y. Zhang, X. Huang, X. Zhang, J. Li, Y. Huang, K. Li, H. Weng, Y. Xu, and Y. Zhang. Exploration of the existence forms and patterns of dissolved oxygen molecules in water. *Nano-Micro Letters*, 16: article no. 208, 2024.